

AUTHENTIC ASSESSMENT TOOLS IN ASIAN HISTORY INPUT TO A DEVELOPED HIGHER ORDER THINKING SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to determine if the authentic assessment tools in Asian History is effective in enhancing the students' higher order thinking skills in terms of analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating. The subjects of this study were the one hundred twelve (112) students from Grade Seven classes of Anilao National High School which are chosen thru the stratified, the quota, the criterion, and the convenience sampling procedures. The study used several instruments such as researcher made survey questionnaire, pre-test, post-test, and Lesson Exemplars employing the authentic assessment tool such as observation-based assessment and performance-based assessment. A pre-test and post-test which were administered to the respondents by the researcher. The analysis showed that distribution of the respondents' perceptions on the use of observation-based assessment tools was 3.52 with a verbal interpretation "sometimes". On the other hand, the distribution of the respondents' perceptions in the use of performance bases-assessment tool was 3.50 with the same verbal interpretation "sometimes". On the levels of t-test, there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents in terms of higher-order thinking skills in terms of analyzing skills, synthesizing skills, and evaluating skills. This is supported by the computed p-value 0.000 that is less than the set significance level of 0.005. On the levels of correlation, there is a significant relationship between student's perceptions of the use of authentic assessment tools in Asian history and the level of students' achievement in higher-order thinking skills. The basis of this interpretation is the computed p-value of 0.001 which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Moreover, this is supported by the computed r-value of 0.305. It can be concluded that that observation-based and performance-based assessment used were able to make a noticeable impact especially in the evaluating skill of the respondents. Based on the findings and conclusions made in the study, the following recommendations are given; results of this research may be communicated to proper authorities for possible actions and an intervention to further improve the respondents higher order thinking skills may be proposed. Likewise, the instrument used in this research may be made available for public consumptions it means efforts to modify the instrument for further improvements may be conducted. Furthermore, qualitative research using an interview and/or structured interview guide or even a follow-up or a parallel study may be conducted to further validate the findings of this research. Lastly future researcher who will interested in pursuing this topic may use other variables and this paper may also serve as their reference.

Keywords: assessment tools, observation-based assessment, performance-based assessment, thinking skills